

Using the Traditional Methods of Determining Rabbit's Throat

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Abstract: Initially, during the investigation, 4 rabbits were taken for the experiment and they were divided into 4 experimental groups. First, they are checked by weight, then we check them by palpation. The age of rabbits is determined, so we study the physiology of rabbits.

Keywords: Rabbit breeders, rabbit physiology, palpation, experimental groups, traditional method, development, comparison.

INTRODUCTION. Veterinarians and rabbit breeders will palpate or gently probe (with fingers) a rabbit's abdomen to determine if it is colicky. During the first two weeks of gestation, you should be able to feel the young rabbits in the mother rabbit's womb. But knowing how to handle them without harming the fetus takes some skill. This is just a general guide and unless you are a vet or experienced breeder you should not attempt to palpate a pregnant rabbit yourself. Gently grasp the rabbit's ears and shoulder skin in your right hand. This strengthens the rabbit's upper body.

With your left hand, gently place the rabbit's lower body between its hind legs and pelvis. Gently place your thumb on the right side of your belly and your fingers on the left side. If the rabbit is pregnant, you should feel the developing embryos in her abdomen (Each embryo should feel the size of a grape). If you do not know how to safely palpate an animal, it is recommended that you take your rabbit to a veterinarian. A veterinarian knows how to safely examine your rabbit without harming the fetus. Do not palpate a pregnant rabbit if it has been more than 14 days. May harm the developing fetus. A pregnant rabbit, like a pregnant human, will gain weight during pregnancy. However, this weight is not a big, noticeable difference. The best way to determine if a rabbit is pregnant by weight is to use an accurate digital scale and compare that number to the rabbit's pre-pregnancy weight.

Fig. 1. Determining the size of a rabbit by weight. (kg) (given the same feed)

An average of 0.029 kg (about 0.064 lb) is gained during the first week of pregnancy, and about 0.057 kg (0.126 lb) by the end of the second week. After the second week, the weight of the mushroom does not change significantly. Have the vet do an ultrasound. Ultrasound is the best way to determine the pregnancy of a rabbit, because after the first six days of pregnancy, it reaches 100% accuracy. Your vet can perform an ultrasound to quickly and accurately determine whether or not your rabbit is pregnant.

Fig. 2. Study of the physiology of the rabbit.

The average life expectancy is 7-8 years, but at home, babies can safely live up to 12 years, and in some cases can be observed even longer. If you take proper care of decorative eared rabbits, their lifespan can reach 8-12 years.

Another important criterion for determining the age of rabbits is the jaw of teeth. A rabbit always has white and even teeth. By the age of one year, the teeth are clear, yellow-gray, gray spots, then covered with yellow-gray fur.

Most rabbit breeds reach sexual maturity between three and six months. Female rabbits can become pregnant as early as 12 weeks of age, but this is generally not recommended for the health and safety of the rabbit.

If your rabbit is less than 12 weeks old, it's not strait. However, if she falls between three and six months of age, she may have reached sexual maturity and is likely to become pregnant.

If your rabbit is more than two or three years old, she may be too old to become pregnant. In this case, your rabbit is not pregnant.

Understand rabbit breeding trends. Rabbits are capable of breeding year-round, but male fertility decreases during winter and summer extremes. Rabbits are most likely to become pregnant in the spring or autumn when the weather is mild, but again, a rabbit can become pregnant at any time of the year.

This means that a female rabbit's body is physically prepared for conception within eight hours of meeting a male rabbit.

Female rabbits have a strong instinct to build nests while waiting for offspring. A pregnant rabbit usually covers her nest with fur to protect her nest. If your bird is nesting, she may be pregnant. However, some female rabbits experience a "false pregnancy," in which the bird lays itself but is not actually pregnant. Therefore, nesting is not an accurate way to determine broodiness, although it is maternal instincts.

Separate women from all men. Once you know for sure that your doe is pregnant, it is important to keep her and all male rabbits separate. This is because a man can re-impregnate a woman within hours of giving birth. This can cause a lot of stress for the female rabbit and make it impossible for the female rabbit to wean her first litter until her second birth.

Some animal experts recommend trying to find a way to allow male and female rabbits to interact without sharing the same cage or hutch. This is because it can be difficult to get two rabbits back together after the female gives birth if they are not properly placed during separation. If possible, try to keep their cages next to each other or make it difficult for them to cross each other.

CONCLUSION. As far as palpation of rabbits is concerned, the traditional method of palpation can damage the developing embryo in the rabbit's abdomen and is of little benefit for examination. In order to determine their weight, it is necessary to keep them in the same conditions (not to change different feeds). Changing the food environment causes a change in rabbit body weight and does not give results.

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